

Liver Enzymes of Broiler Birds Fed Diets Containing African Locust (*Parkia Biglobosa*) Beans Stem Bark as Replacement to Antibiotics

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Abstract

This study was carried out in the Department of Animal Science Federal University of Agriculture Zuru, Kebbi State. To assess the liver enzymes level of broilers fed diets containing *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark as replacement to antibiotics, with a view to determine the level of ALT and AST. Two hundred (200) Ross 308 day-old chicks were shared into four (4) experimental treatment groups, and each treatment group was replicated five times, with 10 chicks per replicate in a completely randomized design. Four treatment diets were prepared as follows: T1 contained 0.0% PBSB, T2 contained 0.1% PBSB, T3 contained 0.2% PBSB while T4 contained 0.3% PBSB. The results obtained from this study indicated that there was no significant difference ($P>0.05$) between the treatments on AST and ALT. But numerical variations were observed in all parameters. The highest ALT numerical value was recorded in T3 (9.66iu/L) followed by T4 (8.33iu/L) followed by T1 (7.00iu/L) and lowest value was recorded in T2 (5.00iu/L). The AST values recorded were 8.33iu/L, 6.00iu/L, 6.00 iu/L, 6.00iu/L for T4, T1, T2 and T3 respectively. It is concluded based on the finding of this study that feeding *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark does not pose any serious health challenge to the broiler birds, especially as it related to the liver. Broiler can be fed *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark up 300g as replacement to antibiotics. It is recommended that similar studies should be carried out to ascertain the liver enzymes on broilers.

Keywords: Liver, Enzymes, Broiler bird and African locus beans.

INTRODUCTION

The need for additional protein supplies to promote sustainable monogastric livestock in most tropical area has increased the search for indigenous legumes stem bark for least cost formulation and production, one of such legumes is *Parkia biglobosa* commonly known as African locust bean a tropical tree which is native to Africa and widely distributed in the savannah region (Adewusi, 2016) The tree is usually and carefully preserved by inhabitants of the area where it grows because they are valuable sources of reliable especially the stem bark which serve as source of useful ingredients for poultry feeding (Cambell, 2017). *Parkia biglobosa* has high protein and better amino acids profile that recommended it for use as a protein substitute for human food and animal feed (Odufa *et al.*, 2017).

Parkia biglobosa is a plant that has shown potential as a source of chemotherapeutics compound while many materials and ethno botanical applications of this plant have been reported (Abdulrahman, 2009). Poultry research nutrition is focusing on functional mechanisms to formulate high quality feeds that would improve the efficiency of feed utilization, growth performance and produce the desired meat quality attributes for a long time antibiotics were use to minimized utilization of nutrients in feed and enhance growth performance and production of poultry but consumers are rejecting the use of antibiotics in animals feed because of their association with human and animal health risk (Abdulrahman, 2009).

A broiler is any chicken that is bred and raised specifically for meat production. Most commercial broilers reach slaughter weight between four to seven weeks of age, although slower growing breeds reach slaughter weight at approximately 14 weeks of age (Eyo, 2015).

Liver: Chicken liver is inexpensive, a great source of nutrients, versatile and easy to cook. Rich with iron, folate, and a variety of vitamins and minerals. Chicken liver is rich with essential fatty acids and protein. Chicken liver also contains vitamin B12, vitamin C, vitamin A, vitamin E, copper, choline, folate, niacin, and riboflavin. (Falade, 2018).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

This experiment was conducted at College of Agriculture Zuru, Kebbi State, Nigeria. Zuru is located within the latitude 11° and 11°- 55° North and longitude 4° 45' and 5°- 25° East of the equator. In the northern Guinea Savannah of the South Eastern part of Kebbi State (KBSG, 2003). It is also found in the extreme South Eastern part of the Kebbi State on a hilly terrain and bounded to the North by Danko Wasagu Local Government Area, North west by Yauri Local Government Area, North east by Bukkuyum Local Government Area of Zamfara State and South by Rijau Local Government area of Niger State (Baba *et al.*, 2013).

Sources of Experimental Materials

Stem bark of *Parkia biglobosa* was collected from the hill opposite Federal University of Agriculture Zuru during dry season around December 2024.

Processing of Experimental Materials

Stem bark of *Parkia biglobosa* were sun dried for two weeks. The dried stem bark was then crushed into small particles and grinded into powder stored in a plastic container prior use.

Experimental Diets

Four experimental diets were formulated containing antibiotic (keprocerine) in T1, 0.1kg in T2, 100g of *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark powder in T3, 200g of *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark and T4 300g in addition to other ingredients as shown in table 3 and 4 below.

Table 1: Gross and calculated chemical composition for starting phase

Ingredients	T1 (0.0kg PBSB)	T2 (0.1kg PBSB)	T3 (0.2kg PBSB)	T4 (0.3kg PBSB)
Maize	45.00	45.00	45.00	45.00
Soybean meal	29.00	29.00	29.00	29.00
Groundnut cake	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
Wheat offal	8.00	8.00	8.00	8.00
Fish meal	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Bone meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Blood meal	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Premix	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Salt	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Lysine	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Methionine	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Total	100	100	100	100

Calculated chemical composition

Energy	3030ME kcal/kg	3030ME kcal/kg	3030ME kcal/kg	3030ME kcal/kg
Crude protein (%)	23.9	23.9	23.9	23.9
Calcium (%)	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9
Phosphorus (%)	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8

Key: PBSB (*Parkia Biglobosa* stem bark)

Table 2: Gross and calculated chemical composition for finishing phase

Ingredients	T1 (0.0kg PBSB)	T2 (0.1kg PBSB)	T3 (0.2kg PBSB)	T4 (0.3kg PBSB)
Maize	52.00	52.00	52.00	52.00
Soybean meal	19.25	19.25	19.25	19.25
Groundnut cake	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00
Wheat offal	5.6	5.6	5.6	5.6
Fish meal	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
Bone meal	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Blood meal	2.38	2.38	2.38	2.38
Premix	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21
Salt	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Lysine	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Methionine	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21
Total	100	100	100	100

Calculated chemical composition

Energy	2960ME kcal/kg	2960ME kcal/kg	2960ME kcal/kg	2960ME kcal/kg
Crude protein (%)	19.4	19.4	19.4	19.4
Calcium (%)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Phosphorus (%)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

Key: PBSB (Parkia Biglobosa stem back)

Experimental Design

Complete randomized design (CRD) was used for this experiment, the birds were randomly divided into four dietary treatment groups labeled T1, T2, T3, and T4 Each treatment were replicated five times with 10 broiler birds in each replicate the birds were fed one of the experimental diets for a period of eight weeks, feed and water were given ad-libitum and the birds were managed intensively.

Experimental Birds and Their Management

The birds used for this experiment was sourced from Zarms, Tech-Farm Ibadan, Oyo State Nigeria, two hundred (200) Ross 308 day old broilers were purchased and used for this research. The chicks were brooded for three weeks in a deep liter system during which they were fed one of the experimental starter diets for four weeks while finisher diets were given from five weeks to the end of the experiment. Vaccination and other routine poultry management practice which include daily inspection of the birds for symptom of disease, mortality, cleaning of trough and drinkers were observed to the end of the experiment.

Medication

The chicks were given anti stress in drinking water at their arrival to the experimental site and other medication was done as the case arises.

Experimental Materials

Bottle, hand gloves, cotton wool, spirit, syringes, and needle.

Blood Sample Collection and Processing

At the end of the 56 days (eight weeks) of feeding trial, the birds were fasted overnight, two birds were randomly selected from each replicate for haematological analysis, two (2) ml of blood sample were collected from each of the selected birds in the morning between 6 to 7am Via punctured of wing vein, and dispensed into plain bottles. Biochemical parameters such as AST and ALT concentration was then be determined.

Procedure for Determination Biochemical Parameters

Determination of Aspartate Amino transferase (AST) Activity Assay

Principle: L oxoglutarate+ L aspartate AST L -Glutamate to xaloacetate. Aspartate aminotransferase activity was measure by monitoring the concentration of oxilacetatehydrozone formed with 2,4dinitrophenyl hydrazine.

Reagent: reagent kit containing phosephate buffer (10m(o/1,PH.7,4), L Aspartate (100mmoI/I) L -oxoglutarate (2mmol/I)), ditrophenyl hydrazine (2mmoI/I) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was used.

Procedure: two (2) clean test tube was labeled as test and blank, then to each of the test tubes 0.5ml of substrate buffer solution would be placed and incubated at 37°C for 5 min the 0.1ml of the serum were added to the labeled test and further incubated at 37°C for 40min. to all the test tubes 0.5ml of 2,4 dinitrophenyl hydrazine was added 0.1ml aliquat of serum was added to the test tube labeled blank, the mixture were shaken and allowed to stand at room temperature for 20min after which 5ml of 0.4 NaOH was added to each of the tubes and allowed to stand for 5min. the absorbance was at 546nm after zeroing the instrument using the blank.

Test tube	Test (ml)	Blank (ml)
Substrate buffer solution	0.5	0.5
Was incubate at 37°C for 5min serum.	0.1	
Mixed and incubate at 700 for 30 min 2,4 dinitrophenyl hydrate serum	0.5	0.5
Was mixed and allowed to stand at room temperature for 20 min 0.4 NaOH		0.5
Was mixed and absorbance of test would be read at 546nm after 5min	5.0	5.0

Determination of Alanine Amino Transferes (ALT) Activity Assay

Principle L-Oxoglutarate +Alanine ALT L-Glutamate pyruvate Alanine aminotransferase activity was measured by monitoring the concentrate of pyruvate hydrazine formed with 2,4dinitrophenyl hydrazine through measurement of absorbance apectrophoto metrically at 540nm.

Reagent: A reagent kit was used which contain phosphate buttern (100mmo/l PH7.4), L- Alanine (200mmol/l).

Procedure: Two (2) clean test and blank the two each of the tube 0.5ml of substrate buffer solution was placed and blank respectively then each was be further incubated at 37°C for 30min. To all the test tubes, 0.5ml of 2,4dinitripheny hydrazine was added. The mixture was properly shaken and allowed to stand at room temperature for 30min.5ml of NaOH was added and allowed for 30min to stand for 5min. the absorbance was measure using a spectrophotometer at 546nm after zeroing the instrument with distilled water at the same wave length.

Data Collection

The data was collected on AST, ALT, and their components according to the sample submitted.

Data Analysis

All data collected was subjected to analysis of variance using statistical package (SPSS) significant difference among treatment means was compared using Duncan multiple range test at 5% level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter present then result and discussion of biochemical parameters of broiler fed diets containing *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark as replacement to antibiotic

Table 3: Liver enzymes parameter of broiler fed *Parkia Biglobosa* stem bark powder

Parameters	T1 (0.0g)	T2 (100g)	T3 (200g)	T4 (300g)	SEM
ALT (iu/L)	7.00	5.00	9.66	7.33	0.09
AST (iu/L)	6.00	6.00	6.00		0.47

The value for Aspartate amino (AST) in this study were lower than findings of (Abdulrahman, 2009), Who reported 21.40-27u/l for Aspartate amino transferase of broiler fed diets containing different phytogetic fed additives. However, the value for Aspartate amino transerase obtaining in this research was within the reference range report (Oshomikan, 2016) for broiler. The activity of Aspartate amino transferase (ALT) in this research was lower than the findings of (Ntui and Bakayo, 2018). The reduction in Alanine amino treferase (ALT) is an indication of better liver function (Ntui and Bakayo, 2018).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

It was concluded base on the findings of this study that feeding *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark does not pose any serious health challenge to the broiler birds, especially as it related to the liver.

Broiler can be fed *Parkia biglobosa* stem bark up 300g as replacement to antibiotics. It is recommended that similar studies should be carried out to ascertain the liver enzymes on broilers.

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